

The Multiponent

Aku L. T. Jutila – Independent Scholar

Abstract

The Multiponent is a mathematical work for the proposal of variants to exponents for the other four elementary arithmetic operations. The visual notation is attached at the end of the document. To note, the notation is an imperfect drawing, and should not be considered the final style. The notation only applies to individual symbols, and a notation for accommodating the system to equations requiring multiple attached symbols in terms would be needed to be created.

I. Multiponent

Basic arithmetic utilizes exponents as notation for repeated multiplication¹. However, it could be argued that there is no logical obstacle to the extension of its logic to the other elementary arithmetic operations². Utilizing the visual notation, the following system, using the same general rules as exponents, is proposed:

On the top-right, exponents shall continue existing as normal, $3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$ and so on.

On the bottom-right is the inponent, for division, $3 \div 3 \div 3 \div 3 \div 3 \div 3 \div 3 \div 3$ and so on.

On the bottom-left is the adponent, for addition, $3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3$ and so on.

On the top-left is the subponent, for subtraction, $3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3$ and so on.

The logic of the system is that each “ponent” occupies its own corner around the number, to designate which ponent is utilized for in the equation. And ponents, as with exponents, could help make equations more visually concise. To note however, the system at this level is designed for basic simple

¹ Morris Kline, *Mathematics for the Nonmathematician* (Dover Publ'ns 1985).

² Alfred North Whitehead & Bertrand Russell, *Principia Mathematica* vol. 1 (2d ed. Cambridge Univ. Press 1925).

arithmetic, rather than including complexities, bracketing them for possible future expansion of the system.

II. Conclusion

A base system for the multiponent has been established. A sketch of the visual notation has been attached. Such system could possibly be used in matters such as making simple arithmetic equations more concise.

References

Morris Kline, *Mathematics for the Nonmathematician* (Dover Publ'ns 1985).

Alfred North Whitehead & Bertrand Russell, *Principia Mathematica* vol. 1 (2d ed. Cambridge Univ. Press 1925).

Visual notation

Subtraction 2 2 Multiplication
 3
Addition 2 2 Division